

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE FORMATION IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

K.Sh. Jamalova

Namangan State University, 1 course doctoral student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15590006>

Abstract. *The given article discusses the emergence and essence of the concept of emotional intelligence, the pedagogical conditions for the formation of emotional intelligence in elementary school students.*

Keywords: *emotion, inner voice, empathy, emotional intelligence, brain stem, hippocampus, new cortex (neocortex), thinking, memory and speech centers.*

INTRODUCTION

It is important to note that our emotions are always with us, but we hardly ever listen to them. Typically, we become aware of our emotions only after they have accumulated and finally gone out of control. However, if we are attentive, we can feel them at a subtler level long before they manifest with such intensity. Emotions have their own programming and schedule. But in our intense, fast-paced lives, there is no space or airtime for them, and so they retreat underground. This overwhelming mental and emotional activity drowns out the quieter inner voice that offers access to internal sources of confidence sources that help us stay afloat in the ocean of life.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of emotional intelligence was first introduced into the field of science in 1990 by researchers J. Mayer and P. Salovey. D. Goleman is also widely recognized as one of their prominent followers. Through his numerous speeches, publications, and appearances at scientific congresses, Goleman brought the term emotional intelligence into public attention.

Back in the early 1930s, L.S. Vygotsky identified the issue of studying the structure and interrelations of emotions and how they connect with more complex psychological systems, and he defined it as a fundamental task of scientific psychology. In the 1940s, psychologist David Wechsler proposed that various effective components of intelligence play a vital role in determining a person's success in life.

Experienced psychologist John Gottman, while studying emotional intelligence (EQ), demonstrated that the behavioral stereotypes we usually consider correct do not actually help develop a child's emotional intelligence. He emphasized the following:

- Pay attention to the child's emotions;
- Use emotional expression as an opportunity to teach and connect with your child;
- Show empathy and try to better understand the child's mood;
- Help your child cope with difficult situations and solve problems.

Researchers such as K.S. Kuznetsova, I.N. Meshcheryakova, and others study the pressing issues of emotional intelligence across various age groups. T.I. Solodkova analyzes the resource potential of emotional intelligence in teachers' professional activities. A.K. Kravtsova examines the connection between emotional intelligence and leadership within teams.

Emotions are our psychological fuel. Emotional intelligence is the ability not to waste that fuel. The author of this term, the renowned psychologist Daniel Goleman, in his book *Emotional Intelligence*, states that certain types of competencies are necessary for emotional intelligence to be effective. He explains this valuable and complex resource by distinguishing two categories of emotions: personal and social.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study utilized methods such as observation, direct interviews, questionnaires, and pedagogical experiments. Our pedagogical experiment focused on implementing an educational program aimed at:

- analyzing emotional expressions,
- managing emotional charge and release,
- and role-playing activities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the context of emotional intelligence, Goleman discusses the influence of brain evolution on our emotions and behaviors. He describes how over millions of years of evolution, the human brain developed three main areas:

- Brain stem, located at the base of the brain and a continuation of the spinal cord. It regulates physiological functions and instinctive reactions. This is the most primitive part of the brain.

- Hippocampus and amygdala developed later and are positioned slightly above the brain stem. In the 1980s, Joseph LeDoux described the role of the amygdala as being responsible for processing visual and other sensory information and for generating emotional responses. In certain situations, the amygdala can "hijack" the brain, taking over before logical thought can occur and forcing an immediate reaction. Mammals or humans with a removed amygdala are incapable of experiencing emotions. It catalyzes impulsive actions that override logical thinking.

- Neocortex (new cortex) – the large, highly developed upper part of the brain responsible for thinking, memory, and language functions.

During the process of evolution, emotions and cognitive abilities—the two main functions of the brain responsible for behavior—are located in different zones. Moreover, emotional centers receive information earlier than cognitive centers, often triggering a rapid and sometimes intense response. This can lead to consequences that may be disastrous for a person.

If we are not aware of the situation and do not control our emotions, we might allow inappropriate emotional reactions that hinder our ability to consider other options. However, emotions have their own kind of "wisdom," and we must learn to use them especially for intuition.

When people encounter stimuli that provoke intense fear, anger, or despair, for example, the first impulse comes from the amygdala. Before the rational mind engages, the brain switches to survival mode, which promotes instinctive responses that may or may not be appropriate.

Structure of Emotional Intelligence (EI). For describing EI functioning, scholars have proposed a system consisting of five elements: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills. Each of these elements has specific characteristics:

- **Self-awareness** – Understanding how your emotions affect your behavior; being guided by your values in decision-making; recognizing your strengths and weaknesses and learning from experience (self-esteem); confidence in yourself, your abilities, values, and goals.

- **Self-regulation** – Managing moods; controlling stress, positivity, and goal orientation; staying calm and thinking rationally under pressure; possessing emotions; reliability and self-control.
- **Motivation** – Enjoying problem-solving; striving for success; accountability; initiative; optimism; choosing goals based on personal preferences.
- **Empathy** – The ability to adopt another perspective; openness and honesty; avoiding stereotypes about others; knowledge of cultures.
- **Social skills** – Abilities such as influencing and persuading; communicating effectively, including with colleagues; listening, collaborating, conflict resolution; the ability to inspire and lead; initiating and managing change; understanding others' emotions.

According to Daniel Goleman, individuals with these traits are more likely to succeed in leadership positions. For instance, he cites various sources confirming that top managers with high levels of EI perform better. He also describes several humorous situations illustrating how EI manifests in the workplace.

Daniel Goleman believes that emotional intelligence (EI) can be developed. In collaboration with the Hay Group, he created an Emotional Competency Inventory to assess and enhance EI. This inventory condenses the original five EI components into four categories:

- **#1 Self-Awareness:**
 - Understanding one's own emotions and their meaning;
 - Realistically perceiving one's strengths and weaknesses;
 - Confidence in oneself and one's abilities.
- **#2 Self-Management:**
 - Controlling emotions;
 - Honesty and reliability;
 - Adaptability and dedication.
- **#3 Social Awareness:**
 - Empathy and the ability to perceive others' thoughts and perspectives;
 - Understanding group dynamics and interpersonal relationships;
 - Paying attention to others' needs.
- **#4 Social Skills:**
 - Helping others in their personal development;
 - The ability to influence people;
 - Excellent interpersonal communication skills;
 - The ability to adapt management styles;
 - Conflict resolution and mediation skills;
 - Building and maintaining relationships;
 - Teamwork abilities.

The idea that success largely depends on communication skills is not new; therefore, Daniel Goleman has sometimes been criticized for presenting well-known ideas with a fresh packaging. Goleman himself does not hide the origins of his ideas and often credits the work of his colleagues. In 2000, Charles Woodruff analyzed Goleman's concept of EI and concluded:

- When Daniel Goleman writes that EI is inherent to every person by nature, yet simultaneously claims it can be developed, he contradicts himself.
- Using questionnaires to measure EI, especially in terms of reliability, is not sufficient.

• The manifestations of EI or the competencies proposed by Goleman—such as self-confidence and leadership—are not entirely new and have long been recognized as factors in high achievement.

Regardless of how valid these criticisms are, Daniel Goleman has undoubtedly enriched management theory with his work on emotional intelligence. He took complex ideas related to human behavior and biological evolution and translated them into a simple, understandable format. As a result, many have embraced it. We can use our intellect to better manage our emotions and apply emotional awareness effectively.

CONCLUSIONS

For concluding the suggested the above ideas, each subject taught in primary school is ideally suited to be integrated with emotional learning, and incorporating the emotional component helps students learn academic subjects more successfully. Once modern pedagogical technologies are effectively introduced into the educational process, they not only ensure that all students assimilate learning materials successfully but also contribute to the development of emotional intelligence.

REFERENCES

1. Bolotova A., Molchanova O. *Developmental and Youth Psychology*. – Moscow: 2012. P.528.
2. Nishonova Z.T. *Increasing the Role of the Teacher in Fostering Creative Independent Thinking // Education and Upbringing*. 2001. N. 1-2. Pp. 40-42.
3. Gileva E.A. *History of the Development of the Project Method in Russian Schools // Science and School*. 2007. Issue 4. Pp. 13-15.
4. Goleman D. *Emotional Intelligence. Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. Moscow: Mann, Ivanov and Ferber, 2017. P. 544.
5. Gruzikova S.Yu., Kamaleeva A.R. *The Keys Method: History of Development and Use in Education // SISP*. 2013. Issue 6 (26).
6. Koroleva N.M. *Using Play Activities in Lessons for Primary School Foreign Language Learning // SISP*. 2010. Issue 4.
7. Mariko V.V., Mikhaylova E.E. *Reflection in Pedagogy: Stages of Formation and Development Tools // UNN Bulletin*. 2013. N. 6-1.
8. *New Pedagogical and Information Technologies in Education: Textbook. Aid for Students of Higher Educational Institutions / E.S. Polat, M.Yu. Bukharkina, M.V. Moiseeva, A.E. Petrov*. 3rd edition, revised and supplemented – Moscow: Academia, 2010. P. 272.
9. Selevko G.K. *Modern Educational Technologies: Textbook. Manual*. – Moscow: People’s Education, 1998. P. 256.